

THE ROLE OF RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S SPORTS

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Annotation: The development of sports in Uzbekistan, the promotion of healthy lifestyles among the population, especially the growing involvement of the younger generation, women in physical culture and sports are important. The article analyzes these issues.

Keywords: sports, world arenas, Zulfya State Prize, badminton, chess, checkers, rhythmic gymnastics

Today, due to the high attention paid to sports by the leadership of our government, the achievements of our country's female athletes in the world arenas are enormous. Because of independence, we had a lot of opportunities. It is both an obligation and a duty for us to act accordingly, to increase our achievements in all spheres. Due to the care of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for women, the attitude to the sport of rhythmic gymnastics, which is one of the important factors in restoring, strengthening and protecting their health, has changed radically during the years of independence. After all, sport is an ambassador of solidarity, friendship, goodness, a symbol of maturity.

"We must do everything possible to create decent conditions for more than 17 million sisters, daughters, mothers and grandmothers living in our country," said President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his December 29, 2020 Address to the Oliy Majlis.¹

Continuing his speech, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted that the number of grants for girls from needy families will be doubled to 2,000, and special scholarships will be introduced for girls with excellent grades and in need of social protection².

It is known that the role of women in our social life and cultural life is incomparable and of great importance. In order to commemorate the culture of ancient ancestors, to celebrate the "Year of Women" in 1999 in Jizzakh, in 2001 in Shakhrisabz (Kashkadarya region) was organized the Republican Festival "Tomaris Games". It has become a tradition to hold the Women's Sports Decade, which is held annually on March 8, Women's Day. More than 1 million women are actively involved in table tennis, badminton, chess, checkers, rhythmic gymnastics and athletics.

In recent years, many women rhythmic gymnasts have achieved good results in international competitions. Such a process serves to enrich our national sports culture. Oksana Chusovitina and Larina Mukhitdinova are becoming world sports stars.

In 2005, gymnastics began to work in our country. Her main activity is mass gymnastics performances for women of all ages, combining rhythmic sports and general

¹Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. December 29, 2020. www.president.uz

²That source.

gymnastics exercises and movements.

Many sports federations organize special courses for women and train instructors on the ground to develop the sport³. This, in turn, contributes to the development and popularity of girls' sports.

Today, almost 50% of women are regularly involved in sports, the number of our professional athletes is growing, and 44 girls have been awarded the Zulfiya State Prize for their achievements in this field.

One of the important aspects is that the Children's Sports Development Fund operates under the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic.

The development of sports in our country, the promotion of a healthy lifestyle among the population, especially the wide involvement of the younger generation, women in physical culture and sports, the full support of young athletes are among the priorities of state policy.

Great attention is paid to the construction of modern sports complexes in all regions of the country, including remote villages, to further increase the scale of physical culture and sports among the population, especially to attract women and train highly qualified women for the training process.

Also, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a decree on November 7, 2016 "On measures to further develop gymnastics in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 18, 2016 "On the Republican Specialized Olympic Reserve Sports School for Children and Youth Gymnastics." Our federation, in cooperation with a number of ministries and organizations, is consistently working on the implementation of the decisions of the "On measures to improve the quality of education."

Developed on the initiative of President Sh.M.Mirziyoev and approved on February 7, 2017, the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 includes protection of motherhood and childhood, ... strengthening women's and girls' health, including physical culture and sports. measures related to popularization are covered.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 2018 PF-5368 "On measures to radically improve the system of public administration in the field of physical culture and sports" and President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 16, 2018 PF-3610 "On measures to further develop football" The decision has created great opportunities for the country's physical culture and sports, including football officials. In pursuance of these resolutions and decrees, promising changes are taking place in the sports of our country, especially in football.

In particular, the adoption of a new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Culture and Sports" on September 4, 2015 raised the development of the industry to a new level⁴.

One of the urgent tasks is to acquaint our children and young generation with sports from childhood, to arouse in them a passion and love for sports, to bring them up physically

³ From the practice of the Gymnastics and Synchronized Swimming Federations of Uzbekistan.

⁴ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions" for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T., Xalq sozi gazetasi. February 8, 2017 No. 28 (6722).

and spiritually.

In short, due to the state's attention to the development of women's and children's sports in rhythmic gymnastics, a healthy lifestyle is becoming a way of life in our society.

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